

Fabrication of Carbon Fiber Reinforced Aluminum Composites by Roll Diffusion Bonding Method

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ABSTRACT

The purpose of this study is to investigate the possibility of the continuous fabrication of CF/Al composites with plasma spray and rolls. The advantage of this method is considered to be the high productivity of CF/Al composites, that is, annoying carbon fibers are rapidly fixed by sprayed aluminum without foil and organic binder and composite can be continuously produced by rolls. Tensile strength of 312MPa(Vf:0.12) was successfully attained and the result ascertained the possibility of this method. But broken fibers were observed in the samples. The causes of fiber breakages were pointed out by observation of the samples and model experiments.

INTRODUCTION

Recent worldwide tendency to save energy requires lightening of movable structures such as automobiles and aircrafts. As high strength-to-weight and high stiffness-to-weight ratios are important in that case, FRP is mainly used. But it is lacking in high temperature strength, FRM is expected to come widely into the world. CF/Al composites, which a lot of investigators have been tried to make (1), have not only their thermal and mechanical properties but also have economic advantages including relatively low cost matrix and potential low-cost fiber. A lot of processes to manufacture CF/Al composites have been investigated also in Japan.

The purpose of this study is to look into the possibility of the continuous fabrication process of CF/Al composites with plasma spray and rolls. Both of plasma-spraying and roll diffusion bonding were only used for boron fiber reinforced metals (2)(3). The advantage of this method is high productivity of CF/Al composites, that is, sprayed aluminum can rapidly fix annoying carbon fibers without foil and organic binder and rolling continuously produces composites. Therefore the reduction of cost expected by this method is industrially meaningful.

EXPERIMENTAL

Fabrication Of Preformed Sheet

The fabrication method of preformed sheet by plasma spray is shown in Fig.1.

The multifilament yarn of 12,000 carbon fibers was spread to 12cm in the flow of air. The filaments were wound on a drum of which diameter is 60cm and the width is 16cm. Rotating this drum at constant speed(73rpm), aluminum was plasma-sprayed on the aligned filaments. According to reference (4), plasma-sprayed aluminum contained 0.98 weight percent oxide and it is comparable to this study. Carbon fiber employed in this study was PAN based HT type. The properties of fiber is given in Table 1. Fiber diameter distributed between 6 and 8 μ m. Aluminum was Plasmalloy-100D. Nominal chemical analysis of the starting powder is given in Table 2. The plasma spray system used in this study was Plasmadyne 80kw-SG-100.

Fabrication Of CF/Al Composites

The fabrication method of CF/Al composites is shown in Fig.2. The pre-formed sheet obtained (120mm x 1,800mm) was cut into pieces (55mm x 110mm) and these were piled up and wrapped with an aluminum foil. The pile (40 layers), sandwiched by plates of mica and stainless steel plates (8mm thick), was heated and roll diffusion bonded in air. Rolling was repeated as the roll distance was controlled to keep the load constant. The load was measured by load cells attached on the rolling machine. Rolling variables included temperature, rolling load and rolling times. Owing to experimental circumstances, long heating was necessary. So vacuum apparatus was prepared to heat samples in it. After being heated, sample was taken out of it and rolled in air. Anyway the heated samples were exposed to air and a little oxidized.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Preformed Sheet

Fig.3 shows the preformed sheet employed in this study. The spraying condition of this sheet is given in Table 3. In general carbon fibers were covered well with aluminum and uncoated fibers were not so much observed.

Fabrication Of Composites In Air

Roll diffusion bonding made the pile of 40 preformed sheets into 2mm-thick composite. The samples produced in air were tensile tested, but no sufficient ultimate tensile strength was attained. Dissolving matrix by HCl solution, carbon fibers were taken out of sample. There were a lot of broken fibers. Fibers which remained longer than 20mm were tensile tested and the result showed deterioration of fibers from original strength of 2.76GPa down to 2.02GPa. It became clear that breakage and deterioration of fibers occurred not during spraying but during rolling. Fig.4 shows the fiber ultimate tensile strength after an hour heating in air at various temperatures. Deterioration of fiber strength begins at 723K. According to Fig.5 carbon fiber rapidly deteriorates in air depending on heating time, and the strength became below half of its original strength. Considering these results, fibers in the sample deteriorated because of oxidation during heating in air.

Observation of these fibers by SEM showed such appearance as something, suspected as oxide, partially coated fibers (Fig.6). Fig.7 shows the absorbed current micrograph of sample. Surface oxidation film was removed by argon ion sputtering. White areas surround some fibers and disperse in the matrix. White area observed here corresponds with coatings previously observed by SEM. Fig.8 shows the result of oxygen analysis of a) white area and b) dark area by Auger Electron Spectroscopy. Results were evaluated by relative ratio of oxygen peak height (at 503 eV) to aluminum peak height (at 68 eV). Oxygen was detected little from the dark area and much more from white area compared with dark area. The shape of aluminum peak of dark area was metallic but that of white area was deformed. Considering these results, white area must be oxides.

Fabrication Conditions Of Composites

As long heating time was necessary, sample was held in vacuum during heating time in order to prevent severe deterioration of fibers caused by oxidation. Fig.9 shows the relation between tensile strength of composite ($V_f:0.12$) and rolling number of times at constant heating temperature (873K) and load

(6.9 x 10³, 11.4 x 10³kg). In case of lower load (6.9 x 10³kg), the sample which was rolled 9 times still contained some interlamina pores (Fig.10-a) and tensile strength was just above 180MPa. Delamination occurred to this sample by tensile test. 10 times rolling could consolidate the sample comparatively well as shown in Fig.10-b. And maximum tensile strength of 278MPa was attained. Further rolling rather caused reduction of tensile strength of composite. So fibers were taken out of 10 times and 20 times rolled samples by HCl solution. Ultimate tensile strength was 2.94GPa at 10 times and was reduced to 2.02GPa at 20 times. This result is related to the deterioration of composite. In case of higher load (11.4 x 10³kg), ultimate tensile strength reached 299MPa at fifth rolling. It didn't go up depending on increased rolling times. As the sample tore in the transverse direction at 10 times rolling, no more rolling was performed. Fig.11 shows the relation between tensile strength of composite and rolling times at lower temperature (833K). In case of higher load (11.4 x 10³kg), composite strength reached maximum value (312MPa) at 8 times and the level was kept until 13 times rolling. Thereafter composite strength showed the tendency to inferiority. The fibers taken out of 16 times rolled sample were only slightly deteriorated. In case of lower load (6.9 x 10³kg), the sample attained 306MPa.

These experimental results can be briefly described as follows. Composite tensile strength is about 200MPa until effective adhesion between sheets are obtained. But it goes up to about 300MPa by effective adhesion of sheets and effective flow of matrix. By the way deterioration of carbon fiber proceeds depending on fabrication time, favorable combination of heating time and rolling times which can fully consolidate the sample before severe fiber deterioration occurs should be selected. In this study σ_c/σ_{LOM} , the ratio of actual tensile strength of the specimen to the strength expected by law of mixture, reached 0.76 which is high enough for the rough experiment. Shortening of heating time can develop this value.

Fiber breakage was generally observed in every sample. A model experiment was tried with mono-filament and plates of sprayed aluminum. The result was that the load higher than 6 x 10³kg broke the fiber. Though this result is not directly applicable to this experiment, it suggests that higher load severely breaks fibers. So fabrication of composite at 5 x 10³kg was tried, but lots of fibers broke. Fig.12 shows typical fiber breakages. The fiber breakage shown in Fig.12-a seems to have occurred by fiber contact. And that shown in Fig.12-b appears to have been locally bent to fracture by non-uniform distribution of matrix. These kinds of breakages may result from structural defects of pre-formed sheet. Considering that contact of fibers and non-uniform distribution of matrix are main defects, model experiments were performed with mono-filaments and aluminum foils. A composite model which consists of crossed fibers and aluminum foils was heated up to 833K and rolled. But the fibers didn't break even at the crossing point. So with high temperature oxidized foils instead of normal ones, same experiment was performed. In this occasion one of the fibers broke at the crossing point. Considering the latter case, thick oxide film resisted fibers to sink into the foils and stress concentration occurred at the crossing point of fibers. So the fiber broke because of its local excessive bending. Next composite model which consists of fiber, foils and another foil to investigate the effect of nonuniformly distributed matrix. This composite model was also heated up to 833K and rolled. The fiber of this case broke only at the aluminum step. These model experiments show that both cases lead to fiber breakage and these cases are often found in samples, so they should be eliminated.

Referring to the idea of law of mixture, fiber breakage will be further discussed. Law of mixture for continuous fibers is given by

$$\sigma_c = \sigma_f V_f + \sigma_m (1 - V_f)$$

σ_c : ultimate tensile strength of composite

σ_{fu} : fiber breaking stress

σ_m^* : matrix strength at fiber fracture strain

In case of discontinuous fibers, law of mixture is given by

$$\sigma_c = \sigma_{fu}V_f(1-L_c/2L) + \sigma_m^*(1-V_f)$$

L : actual fiber length

L_c : critical fiber length

As the samples produced in this study contain various length of fibers, mixture of both equations should be considered. According to the latter equation, critical length fiber doesn't fully play the role of reinforcement. The sample rolled 10 times at 833K by load of 11.4×10^3 kg included a lot of fibers of which length were 20 or 30 times aspect ratio. Though critical fiber length of carbon fiber is not clear, these quite shortly broken fibers must contribute negatively to composite ultimate tensile strength. As the fiber strength of the 16 times rolled sample was not so much deteriorated, the reduction of composite tensile strength after 13 times rolling can be rather explained by this idea. Until 13 times rolling, only the reduction of sample thickness occurred and no extension of sample was observed. This is because the rolling before 13 times were at the stage of consolidation. The internal compression which works on crossed fibers is not so large by this stage. But after this stage, the load directly compresses the crossed fibers with oxide phases, so the fibers are easily broken.

Fig. 13 shows the dependence of bending strength of composite on volume fraction of carbon fiber. When volume fraction increases, bending strength tends to deviate from law of mixture. The causes are considered as follows. More fibers lead to fracture because of the higher possibility of fiber contact. And according to the fact that load-elongation curve of composite approaches straight line, that is, the composite becomes more brittle when volume fraction is increased, high- V_f composites become more sensitive to broken fibers produced during fabrication and pores remain in matrix.

CONCLUSION

CF/Al composites were produced by plasma spray and roll diffusion bonding process in air. Tensile strength of 312MPa ($V_f:0.12$) was successfully attained by this method and the possibility of continuous fabrication of CF/Al composites was ascertained. Fiber breakages will be reduced by uniform matrix distribution, prevention of fiber contact and control of atmosphere during heating and rolling to reduce oxidation of composite. Uniform matrix distribution will also reduce meander of fibers. Performing these improvement, ultimate tensile strength of composite will approach law of mixture. Now, further investigation to spread multi-filament yarn of carbon fibers is necessary. And plasma spray system is originally adjusted to surface treatment, powder mesh, fluidity of powder and other parameters should be changed to adapt to CF/Al composite fabrication. These improvements will lead this fabrication process to success.

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Table 1. Properties of carbon fiber.

Diameter	7 μ m
Fracture stress	2.76GPa
Young's modulus	233GPa
Fracture strain	1.48
Specific gravity	1.76

Table 2. Nominal chemical analysis of aluminum powder.

(Plasmalloy 100-D)

Element	Concentration (Weight percent)
Si	0.062
Mg	<0.01
Cu	<0.01
Fe	0.11

Table 3. Plasma-spraying conditions used for the manufacture of preformed sheets.

Powder	Plasmalloy 100-D
	Powder size : -325mesh (78.2 μ m)
Gases	Arc gas : argon
	Powder gas : argon
Spray stand-off distance:	8cm

Fig.1 Fabrication method of preformed sheet.

Fig.2 Fabrication method of composite.

Fig.3 Optical micrographs of preformed sheet produced by plasma spray. (a) Transverse section; (b) longitudinal section.

Fig.4 Relation between tensile strength of carbon fiber and heating temperature.

Fig.5 Relation between tensile strength of carbon fiber and heating time in air.

Fig.6 Scanning electron micrograph of carbon fiber taken out of sample.

Fig.7 Absorbed current micrograph of sample.

Dark area(a) and white area(b) were analyzed.

Fig.8 Oxygen analysis of sample by auger electron spectroscopy.

Fig.9 Relation between tensile strength of CF/Al composite (Vf:0.12) and rolling number of times. Heating temperature:873K. Rolling load:6.9 x 10³, 11.4 x 10³kg.

Fig.10 Optical micrographs of CF/Al composites at different rolling times. (a) 9 times ;(b) 10 times.

Fig.11 Relation between tensile strength of CF/Al composite ($V_f:0.12$) and number of rolling times at constant heating temperature (833K) and load (6.9×10^3 , 11×10^3 kg).

Fig.12 Optical micrographs of typical broken fibers observed in sample.

Fig.13 Dependence of bending strength of CF/Al composite on volume fraction of carbon fiber.